

Table SM5. PERMANOVA and PERMDISP pairwise comparison analyses based on a Bray Curtis similarity matrix of a macrofaunal community of the continental slope and São Paulo plateau in Santos Basin, SW Atlantic, between depths (m). Data were fourth-root transformed. Significant values indicated by $p < 0.05$.

		PERMANOVA				PERMDISP			
Source	df	SS	MS	Pseudo-F	P(perm)	df1	df2	F	P(perm)
De	6	26610	4435	7.2769	0.001	6	52*	4.8242	0.008
Res	52	31692	609.46						
Pairwise comparison									
Groups (Depth)		t		P(perm)	Unique perms	P(MC)	t		P(perm)
400, 700		2.2292		0.001	920	0.002	6.46E-02		0.966
400, 1000		2.6083		0.001	912	0.001	0.61972		0.588
400, 1300		3.1138		0.001	977	0.001	0.26308		0.826
400, 1900		3.6013		0.001	989	0.001	1.90E-02		0.99
400, 2400		3.4309		0.002	930	0.001	2.5403		2.90E-02
400, 2200		3.9289		0.001	969	0.001	3.8548		4.00E-03
700, 1000		1.6659		0.001	921	0.009	0.35319		0.798
700, 1300		2.0352		0.001	973	0.002	0.12292		0.91
700, 1900		2.7563		0.001	989	0.001	8.67E-02		0.959
700, 2400		2.9563		0.002	930	0.001	1.9429		0.16
700, 2200		3.4084		0.001	981	0.001	2.738		3.10E-02
1000, 1300		1.2765		0.048	983	0.112	0.32629		0.8
1000, 1900		2.4168		0.001	991	0.001	0.74841		0.491
1000, 2400		2.7393		0.001	927	0.002	3.0129		1.50E-02
1000, 2200		3.1908		0.001	983	0.001	4.4795		3.00E-03
1300, 1900		1.9768		0.001	993	0.002	0.32445		0.777
1300, 2400		2.5074		0.001	951	0.001	2.7092		4.30E-02
1300, 2200		2.9535		0.001	982	0.001	3.9691		7.00E-03
1900, 2400		1.9071		0.002	977	0.002	2.9355		5.00E-03
1900, 2200		2.1028		0.001	994	0.002	4.4938		1.00E-03
2400, 2200		1.3453		0.004	946	0.076	0.38303		0.741